

Studies on the Amine Exchange Reactions in C-Mannich Bases

Y. D. KULKARNI* and VIPIN KUMAR AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 1 December 1980, revised 6 August 1981, accepted 7 January 1982

Amine exchange reactions are extended to C-Mannich bases derived from 6-methoxy-1-tetralone and the reaction intermediate during exchange reaction was isolated and characterised.

AMINE exchange reactions have been utilized in C-alkylation^{1,2}, cyclisation of certain compounds³⁻⁶, and in the synthesis of such Mannich bases⁷, which could not be prepared by direct condensation. Usually the primary aromatic amines do not give Mannich bases on direct condensation, while they can be obtained by the exchange reactions. Blicke and Burckalter⁸ could not prepare the Mannich bases from acetophenone, formaldehyde and aniline hydrochloride, but the product β -arylamino ketone was easily obtained by Craig *et al*⁹, using the amine exchange reactions between β -diethylamino ketone and aniline.

Mannich bases¹⁰ from 6-methoxy-1-tetralone (1)¹¹ were prepared with aliphatic secondary amines and with alicyclic secondary amines by the usual Mannich reaction. However, the Mannich bases from 1 with primary arylamines (*p*-chloroaniline/*p*-toluidine) could not be prepared by direct condensation of 1 with paraformaldehyde and amines.

2-Dimethylaminomethyl-6-methoxy-1-tetralone (2) was converted to its methiodide (9) on refluxing with methyl iodide in absolute alcohol. When the methiodide (9) in ethanol was refluxed with piperidine and sodium carbonate, the naphthalenone (5) was isolated as its hydrochloride. The Mannich base (4) was obtained by the amine exchange reaction, when the methiodide (9) was refluxed with morpholine and potassium carbonate in ethanol.

The methiodide (9) also underwent amine exchange reaction with *p*-chloroaniline in ethanol in the presence of potassium carbonate yielding the product 10 which could not be obtained by direct condensation of 1 with paraformaldehyde and *p*-chloroaniline.

Evolution of trimethylamine during the exchange reaction of 2-dimethylaminomethyl-6-methoxy-1-tetralone methiodide (9) indicated that the intermediate in this reaction would be 2-methylene-6-methoxy-1-tetralone (11). Methiodide (9) was heated under reflux with aqueous potassium carbonate in ethanol, which resulted in the Hofmann elimination of methiodide (9) and evolution of trimethylamine. The isolated product, highly unstable, was completely characterized with the help of its

ir, uv and nmr spectra and was identified to be the tetralone (11).

Since the Mannich bases of 1 with *p*-toluidine could not be obtained by direct condensation, methiodide (9) was subjected to exchange reaction with *p*-toluidine and the product 2-(4'-methyl-anilinomethyl)-6-methoxy-1-tetralone (12) was isolated as its hydrochloride. Compound (2) was also subjected to amine exchange reactions with morpholine, piperidine, *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-toluidine and the exchange reactions were successful.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were taken in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. The ir spectra of the Mannich bases showed the presence of C=O bands as strong peaks in the region of 1640-1670 cm^{-1} and $-\text{OCH}_3$ bands in the region of 1140-1160 cm^{-1} .

2-Substituted aminomethyl-6-methoxy-1-tetralone hydrochloride :

Method A : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mole), paraformaldehyde (0.02 mole), amine hydrochloride (0.01 mole) and isopropyl alcohol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 10-15 hr. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under vacuum and cooled. The separated product was filtered and recrystallized from appropriate solvent.

Method B : A mixture of 1 (0.01 mole), paraformaldehyde (0.02 mole), amine (0.01 mole), conc. hydrochloric acid (0.1 ml) in isopropyl alcohol (25 ml) was heated under reflux for 10-15 hr. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under vacuum and cooled. Dry HCl gas was passed into the reaction mixture at 0°. The separated product was filtered and recrystallized from appropriate solvent.

Compounds (I) prepared according to these two methods are presented along with relevant data in Table 1.

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	Method	Melting point °C	Yield %	Crystallisation solvent	% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Calcd.
2.	Me	Me	A	164	55.7	Isopropyl alcohol	5.10	5.19
3.	Et	Et	A	186	40	Ethanol	4.63	4.70
4.	-CH ₂ CH ₂ OCH ₂ CH ₂ -	-	B	168-70	54.4	Ethanol	4.30	4.49
5.	-(CH ₂) ₆ -	-	B	182	68	Isopropyl alcohol	4.36	4.32
6.	-CH ₂ CH ₂ N(OH) ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ -	-	B	162	40	Methanol	8.68	8.62
7.	-CH ₂ CH(OH)CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ -	-	B	176	41	Ethanol	4.17	4.30
8.	-CH ₂ CH(OH)CH ₂ CH ₂ -	-	B	166	38	Ethanol	3.40	3.48

2:	Me	Me
3:	Et	Et
10:	H	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (p)
12:	H	C ₆ H ₄ OH (p)
4:	-CH ₂ CH ₂ OCH ₂ CH ₂ -	-
5:	-(CH ₂) ₆ -	-
6:	-CH ₂ CH ₂ N(OH) ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ -	-
7:	-CH ₂ CH(OH)CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ -	-
8:	-CH ₂ CH(OH)CH ₂ CH ₂ -	-

2-Dimethylaminomethyl-6-methoxy-1-tetralone methiodide (9): A mixture of 2-dimethylamino-methyl-6-methoxy-1-tetralone hydrochloride (2.70 g; 0.01 mole), methyl iodide (6 g; 0.04 mole) and absolute ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed gently for 4 hr. Excess of methyl iodide was removed and the solid mass, separated on cooling, was filtered and recrystallized from absolute ethanol. Yield 2.70 g (72%), m.p. 151-152°. NMR (CDCl₃): δ 2.1-2.4 [-CH₂-N, broad multiplet], δ 2.50-2.70 [2H, quartet (4-CH₂)], δ 3.05 [9H, each singlet,

-N(CH₃)₂], δ 3.30-3.70 [3H multiplet, (3-CH₂ and 2-CH)], δ 3.95 [3H, singlet, (6-OCH₃)], δ 6.75-7.1 [2H, complex quartet, (7-CH and 8-CH aromatic)], δ 7.8-8.1 [1H, complex quartet, (5-CH aromatic)]. M. wt. 375; Analysis: Nitrogen; Found: 3.69%. Calcd.: 3.73%.

2-Substituted aminomethyl-6-methoxy-1-tetralone hydrochloride by the exchange reaction of 9 with amine: 2-Dimethylaminomethyl-6-methoxy-1-tetralone methiodide/hydrochloride (0.005 mole) was dissolved in aq. ethanol (50%; 25 ml). To this were added amine (0.005 mole) and potassium carbonate (0.7 g; 0.005 mole). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hr. Solvent was removed from the reaction mixture and water (25 ml) was added. The separated oil was extracted with ether, the ether layer was distilled and the remaining semi-solid mass was dissolved in dry benzene (25 ml). Dry HCl gas was passed into the benzene solution, cooled to 0°. The separated solid product (I) was filtered and washed with dry benzene and recrystallized from appropriate solvent.

(Analytical data—vide Tables 2A and 2B).

2-Methylene-6-methoxy-3,4-dihydro-1(2)-naphthalenone(11): 2-Dimethylaminomethyl-6-methoxy-3,4-dihydro-1(2)-naphthalenone methiodide (1.9 g; 0.005 mole) was dissolved in aqueous ethanol (50%; 50 ml). To this potassium carbonate

TABLE 2A—WHEN EXCHANGE IS CARRIED OUT WITH THE COMPOUND (9)

Amine to be added	No. of Comp. obtained	Melting point °C	Yield %	Crystallisation solvent	% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
Morpholine	4	170	70	Ethanol	4.47	4.49
Piperidine	5	181	82	Isopropyl alcohol	4.50	4.52
p-Chloroaniline	10	206-7	40	Methanol	3.82	3.98
p-Toluidine	12	176	52	Ethanol	4.15	4.22

TABLE 2B—WHEN EXCHANGE IS CARRIED OUT WITH THE COMPOUND (2)

Amine to be added	No. of the Comp. obtained	Melting point °C	Yield %	Crystallisation solvent	% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
Morpholine	4	169	68	Ethanol	4.34	4.49
Piperidine	5	180-81	71.5	Isopropyl alcohol	4.41	4.52
p-Chloroaniline	10	206	45	Methanol	3.92	3.98
p-Toluidine	12	177	36	Ethanol	4.09	4.22

(1.4 g; 0.01 mole) was added and heated under reflux for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated in vacuum and water (30 ml) was added. It was then extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ether was then removed completely and the residue was recrystallized from absolute ethanol. The product (11) was further purified by preparative layer chromatography, by dissolving in acetone and using benzene/ethyl acetate (2%), solvent mixture. Yield 0.50 g (53.2%), m.p. 121°. IR 1660 (C=C exocyclic and C=O); UV (CHCl₃) λ_{max} 280 (ε-12,600); NMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.05-2.50 [4H, complex quartet, (3-CH₂ and 4-CH₂) skeleton], δ 3.85 [3H, singlet, (6-OCH₃)], δ 6.45-6.80 [2H, quartet (=CH₂)], δ 7.15-7.40 [2H, complex quartet (7-H and 8-CH)] δ 7.88-8.10 [1H, doublet (5-CH)].

References

1. E. C. DUFRU, F. J. MCQUILLIN and R. ROBINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, Pt. 1, 53.
2. H. R. SNYDER, C. W. SMITH and J. M. STEWART, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 200.
3. C. MANNICH and M. BAUROTH, *Chem. Ber.*, 1924, **57**, 1108.
4. (Miss) A. JACOB and J. MADINAVERTIA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, Pt. 2, 1929.
5. G. A. LEVY and H. R. NISBET, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, Pt. 2, 1953.
6. R. H. HARRADENCE and F. LIONS, *Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1939, **72**, 283.
7. J. C. CRAIG, M. MOYLE and L. F. JOHNSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 410.
8. F. F. BLICKER and J. H. BURCKHALTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 451.
9. J. C. CRAIG and M. MOYLE, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1939, Pt. 1, 690.
10. Jubilee Vol. Emit Barrell., 1946, 264.
11. V. C. E. BURNOF, G. H. ELLIOTT and P. LINSTRAD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, Pt. 1, 727.